

ISic3577

Dedication to the Genius Augusti

Language

Latin

Type

dedication

Material

marble

Object

altar or base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2011.06.15

Last Change

2019-07-15 - Jonathan Prag edited on the basis of autopsy and study for 2017 edition

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

Excavated in 1971, in taberna 7 of the west portico in the agora

Coordinates

37.997856, 14.262463

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Halaesa, Antiquarium e sito archeologico di Halaesa, inventory 30594

Physical Description

A section of moulding, composed of off-white marble. Intact at the left end, with a clean cut or break at the right end (both the inscription and moulding are incomplete). The upper edge is rough chiselled, with metal pegs inserted in the top towards each end (8cm from left end, 5 cm from right end). The moulding is made up of four stepped elements, of which the lower (and larger) two carry the inscribed field.

Dimensions

Height 11.8 cm

Width 63 cm

Depth 5-5.3 cm

Layout

Two lines of Latin text incised on the lower two elements of the moulding

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The letters are simply and crudely cut, displaying considerable irregularity in both height and width. Letters are finished with crude triangular serifs, and interpuncts are triangular in form, heavily cut. V is wide, S is shallow, R and P are closed, C and G are not distinguished.

Letter heights:

Lines 1-2: 30-39 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not measured mm

Text

1. Genio · Augusti · et ·[---]

2. L(ucius) · Cornelius ·)(mulieris) · l(ibertus) · Eup|[---]

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

Translation (en)

To the Genius of Augustus and [---] Lucius Cornelius Eupl[us?], freedman of a woman [(set this up)---]

Commentary

Approximately half the text can be assumed to be missing from the right side. Dedications to the Genius of Augustus are commonly paired with dedications to the (Augustan) Lares. Line 1 therefore probably originally read in full: *Genio Augusti et Laribus Augustis*. Line 2 might have contained the name of a second individual, but the available space is probably not sufficient for this, and it is more likely that the cognomen of Cornelius was followed by an indication of the position he held (sevir or sevir Augustalis) and an abbreviation such as *S(ua) P(ecunia) F(ecit)* (i.e. set it up at his own expense).

The final letter of line two could be I, L, or possibly H; it is clear that there is no stroke extending to the right from the upper part of the letter, and it seems unlikely that there is one from the mid-point; but it is impossible to be certain about the base of the stroke. Possible names therefore include Euplus (Greek Εϋπλῦς [http://clas-igpn2.classics.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/igpn_search.cgi?namenoaccents=%CE%95%CE%A5%CE%A0%CE%9B%CE%9F%CE%A5%CE%A3]), which is attested in Sicily, as well as in southern Italy (Campania) and elsewhere, or perhaps Euphraeus (Greek Εϋφραῖος [http://clas-igpn2.classics.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/igpn_search.cgi?namenoaccents=%CE%95%CE%A5%CE%A6%CE%A1%CE%91%CE%99%CE%9F%CE%A3]), which is attested in Hellenistic Sicily including at Akrai, Camarina, and Taormina. A number of other names in Euph- are also possible.

It remains a matter of debate when the Genius of Augustus became the subject of recognised official cult (an important question, because it bridges a gap in the development of ruler cult, which Augustus seems to have avoided embracing directly in Italy), but it seems likely that it may have begun during Augustus' lifetime (see e.g. Letta, C. 2003. *Novità epigrafiche sul culto del Genius Augusti in Italia*, in M. G. Angeli Bertinelli and A. Donati (eds.), *Serta Antiqua et Mediaevalia VI. Usi e abusi epigrafici* (Rome), 217-236, at 224-227). A Sicilian example can be found on Lipari (ISic0771 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0771>]), and perhaps also at Centuripe (ISic0699 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0699>]). Consequently, the exact date is uncertain, but as Manganaro ((1989) 191 no.81 fig.87) observes in discussion of the Lipari example, the lack of distinction between C and G may suggest an earlier (i.e. Augustan) date, rather than later in the first century AD.

Digital identifiers:

TM 645648

Bibliography

Prag, J.R.W., Tigano, G. 2017. Alesa Archonidea : il lapidarium. *Introduzione all'archeologia di Halaesa*. Palermo. At no.14

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